

In Silico Docking Analysis of Andrographolide with HIV-1 Reverse Transcriptase

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ABSTRACT

Acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) is a life threatening infection of the human immune system caused by human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). Effective inhibition of reverse transcriptase activity is a prominent, clinically viable approach for the treatment of AIDS. Few non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIs) have been approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (US FDA) as drugs for AIDS. In order to enhance therapeutic options against AIDS we examined novel herbal compounds of Andrographolide that are known to have remarkable antiviral potency. Our molecular docking have identified one such herbal molecule Andrographolide that may bind HIV-1RT with high affinity to cause non-competitive inhibition. Results are also compared with other US FDA approved drugs. Docking study suggest that the ligand Andrographolide has strong binding interactions with His, Lys 101, Tyr 318, Leu 100, Val 106, Lys 103, Glu 138, Val 179, His 235 amino acids, all of which belong to one or the other catalytic pockets of HIV-1RT. It is expected that these interactions could be critical in the inhibitory activity of the HIV-1RT. Therefore, this study provides an evidence for consideration of Andrographolide as a valuable natural molecule in the treatment and prevention of HIV-associated disorders.

Key Words: AIDS, HIV-1RT, molecular docking, Andrographolide, Inhibition.

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